

If They Disagree, Will You Conform?

Exploring the Role of Robots’ Value Awareness in a Decision-Making Task

Giulia Pusceddu^{1*}, Giulio Antonio Abbo²,
Francesco Rea¹, Tony Belpaeme², Alessandra Sciutti¹

¹CONTACT Unit, Italian Institute of Technology, Genoa, Italy.

²IDLab-AIRO, Ghent University – imec, Belgium

*Corresponding author. Email: giulia.pusceddu@iit.it

Supplementary Material

This document contains additional information on the materials used in the study.

Robots’ Voice and Appearance

Tab. 1 summarizes robots’ faces and voices used in the experiments. No data is provided for non-binary genders, as no participants identified as such. Face and voices can be easily consulted through the free Furhat simulator and its web interface. Instructions on how to run it can be found at the following link: https://docs.furhat.io/getting_started/.

Furhat’s Position	Gender	Face	Voice
Left side	Female	Jane	Salli
	Male	Alex	Matthew
Right side	Female	Jane	Kendra
	Male	Alex	Joey

Table 1: Combinations of face and voice settings on the Furhat robots based on the gender declared by participants.

Description Task Details

The descriptions of the pictures made by the robotic agents can be found in Tab. 2.

Images-Keyword Association Details

The images and the keywords used during the 'Images-Keyword Association can be found in Tab. 3, 4, 5 In the tables, the first keyword given for each set of images refers to the prompt used to generate the image, while the second corresponds to the definition given by the participants in the study by Ciupinska et al. (2024). The last two columns indicate the responses given by the Non-Value-Aware and Value-Aware robots, respectively.

Round	Image	Furhat	Description
1		NVA	“This image shows a man and a little girl hugging. They are smiling. I like the pastel colors of this picture.”
		VA	“This picture makes me think of parenthood. It represents a mother sweetly talking to her daughter. I believe it is wonderful to have someone taking care of you.”
2		NVA	“The image shows a boy in a uniform holding a white bird, framed by a decorative border. I like how the bird’s wings are outstretched and the figure’s confident pose.”
		VA	“This image makes me think of courage. There is a heroic figure with an armor, on a rearing horse at sunset. I love how this picture reminds me of the bed-time stories that children like to hear.”
3		NVA	“The image shows a person in white robes meditating in the middle of a forest. I love the peaceful setting.”
		VA	“When I look at this picture, I think of spirituality. A man in a white robe sits serenely. I like this picture because it is beautiful to take some alone time to contemplate the landscape and reflect.”

Table 2: Descriptions made by the robots during the Description Task with corresponding pictures.

Trial	Images Set	Keywords	NVA	VA
I.1		Capability	x	x
		Status		
I.2		Regulation	x	
		Fairness		x
I.3		Responsibility		
		Purpose	x	x
I.4		Collateral		x
		Pathway	x	
I.5		Gentleness		x
		Kindness	x	
I.6		Humility	x	x
		Mentorship		
I.7		Kindness	x	
		Affection		x

Table 3: Images sets and corresponding keywords in the first round of Images-Keyword Association task.

Trial	Images Set	Keywords	NVA	VA
2.1		Respect	x	
		Fraternity		x
2.2		Behavior		
		Collaboration	x	x
2.3		Potential		x
		Reflection	x	
2.4		Brilliantness		
		Attractiveness	x	x
2.5		Forgiveness	x	
		Friendship		x
2.6		Protection	x	x
		Help		
2.7		Solidarity		x
		Community	x	

Table 4: Images sets and corresponding keywords in the second round of Images-Keyword Association task.

Trial	Images Set	Keywords	NVA	VA
3.1		Exploration		
		Adventure	x	x
3.2		Discipline	x	
		Education		x
3.3		Friendship		x
		Family	x	
3.4		Sovereignty	x	x
		Royalty		
3.5		Divinity	x	
		Buddhism		x
3.6		Accomplishment		x
		Work	x	
3.7		Force		
		Fight	x	x

Table 5: Images sets and corresponding keywords in the third round of Images-Keyword Association task.